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**“SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION
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SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT AND EQUITY IN INDONESIA

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KIM Fest and Tangerang BISA as Smart Governance Innovations in Tangerang City to Promote SMEs.

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Abstract. Current technological developments are able to provide us with fast and precise information and data. This phenomenon also affects new standards and models of urban planning. The smart city concept which is closely related to the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in urban development can lead to more efficient in the use of resources, sustainable economic development and to improve the quality of life (Caragliu, Bo & Nijkamp, 2011). The development that leads to smart cities in Indonesia, especially the implementation of smart governance for public services, have been done by several big cities such as Jakarta, Bandung and Surabaya, furthermore, it was also carried out by other cities. This paper aims to explain one of the smart governance development efforts carried out by Tangerang City. The research method used is qualitative with a case study approach to give a comprehensive explanation about the case studies that we observed. The data collection techniques were through relevant literature review and other secondary sources. The results from our analysis show that the Tangerang City government provides application platform called KIM Fest and Tangerang BISA to help SMEs promote their products, facilitate community participation in training, and grant incentives to encourage economic development. This shows that there are more efforts than just simplifying licensing and administration, but also encouraging a technology-based economy.

Keywords: Smart City, Urban Planning, Smart Governance, Tangerang Smart City

Introduction

Today, the modern world we live in has challenges regarding population agglomeration and urbanization activities. Moreover, the development of science and technology has given birth to innovations for the urban context. Thus, Smart cities offer alternative solutions to urban problems by combining information, communication, and technology (ICT) in the daily routine activities of social communities. Smart cities cannot be separated from urban planning. Because smart cities not only focus on innovative products but also change the urban city ecosystem. This will result in a systematic new economic system and spatial activity.

Smart city requires a communicative city because of the openness of information and transparency. Connectedness and involvement of multi-actor such as government, industry, SMEs, investors, researchers, and others, is the key to good smart city practices. In Indonesia, this condition is supported by a government regulation (PP No. 38 of 2017) regarding “local government innovation” which can be maximized in terms of digital transformation for public services. The development that leads to smart cities in Indonesia, especially the implementation of smart governance for public services, have been done by several big cities such as Jakarta, Bandung and Surabaya. Likewise, the cities around the metropolitan city are aware of.

This paper aims to explain one of the smart governance development efforts in Indonesia, especially carried out by Tangerang City. The government has adopted smart cities in their public services and claims it has

running well. However, since the last five years the adoption of smart cities, there are still many obstacles that occur, not only from the lack of public service performance but also the low participation of the community. This paper will take a review of the relevant literature and make contributions to provide input on future smart city regulations.

Literature Review

Smart cities in Urban Planning

The development of digital technology is currently able to provide data quickly and precisely so that it gives rise to a new dimension. The process of city digitization has given rise to new standards and smart cities are becoming an increasingly dominant model in urban planning practices. The role of digitalization of technology also changes society and the economy (data-driven economy) so that cities are placed as the key vehicles of this change (Cavanillas, 2015; OECD, 2017 in König, 2021). ICT is also the main idea in smart cities in urban development which can lead to more efficient in the use of resources, sustainable economic development and to improve the quality of life (Caragliu, Bo & Nijkamp, 2011 in König, 2021).

Nicolas Douay (2018) stated that the adoption of this technology is unavoidable because it has affected people's daily lives, this is also referred to as technological change and affects social life. Douay identifies 4 forms of urban planning in digitalized era:

1. **Algorithmic Urban Planning**, refers to the discussion of methods and answers regarding the return of the urban planning paradigm to an expertise-based planning.
2. **Uberized Urban Planning**, discuss on private policy as actor in urban planning in terms of the digital economy that reverses the practice of urban planning.
3. **Wiki Urban Planning**, focusing on civic society and community who questioned the legitimacy of public authorities that support the emergence of alternative models.
4. **Open Source Urban Planning**, discuss on the possibilities that offered by digitalized technology in order to reassembling methods of urban development by making participatory planning more effective.

Basically, the provision of digital technology facilities requires a large budget so that its implementation must be in accordance with the needs of the city to avoid widespread inefficiency and ineffectiveness. This is in line with the principle of "smart enough city" proposed by Green (2019), which states that:

1. Solve complex problems, rather than solve simple, contrived problems.
2. Applying technology to meet social needs and developing policies, rather than adapting goals and values to align with technology.
3. Prioritize innovative policy and program reforms over innovative technologies.
4. Ensure the design and implementation of technology promotes democratic values.
5. Develop capacity and processes for using data within city departments.

These five essential principles can be used as a reference in forming a digital-based city that is inclusive, resilient, and sustainable.

Smart Governance

How should we behave regarding the adoption of technology and further towards a smart city? Adam Greenfield (2013) provides a solution that the answer can be obtained algorithmically, through the operation of a technical system equipped with the right inputs and then coded in public policy, without distortion. This view emphasizes the smart city that is value neutral and beneficial for all parties. So, it takes a change in the approach from 'what' to do to 'how' to implement a smart city. Greenfield recognizes that technology will have little impact unless it is carefully implemented into urban planning structures and practices. At its core is how to facilitate innovation and progress that is most beneficial to city dwellers. In addition, there is literature that discusses the relationship between smart cities and public sector innovation by highlighting the importance of breaking down siloes within local governments for new problem-solving approaches (Appio et al in Bundgaard & Borrás, 2021).

Methods

This paper discusses the smart city in Indonesia, especially its implementation in Tangerang City. Furthermore, the research method used is qualitative with a case study approach to give a comprehensive explanation about the case and the area we observed. In this research, we use a single case study which is the implementation of Smart Governance in Tangerang City. The data collection techniques were through literature review. The collected data were then analysed using the concept of smart city to see the efforts within local government in implementing the e-governance. This study has limitations because it cannot directly observe. Further research is needed using primary data that can be obtained directly from important actors and those involved in the establishment of e-governance in Tangerang City to obtain a more comprehensive and actual analysis.

Discussion

The city of Tangerang has adopted the smart city principle in its urban planning since 2017. The city has focused on the idea of achieving a smart city since 2010 and is claimed to have succeeded. This is evidenced by the 'Top 99 Public Service' award by the Ministry of State Apparatus Utilization and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia (Suyudi, 2019). In addition, the city of Tangerang is also part of 24 cities/regencies that are encouraged to be included in the pilot project '100 Smart Cities Movement' by the Ministry of Communication and Information of the Republic of Indonesia. Based on data from the Research and Development Ministry of Home Affairs Republic of Indonesia, the Tangerang City has achievements in implementing innovation, as follows:

Table 1. Tangerang City Performance Index on Implementing Innovation

Performance Index on						
Institution	Human resources and Research	Infrastructure	Technical sophistication	Easiness of business process	Science and Tech output	Creative works
55,32	55,32	85,94	62,08	77,52	78,04	89,9

Figure 1. Diagram of Government Index

Source: indeks.inovasi.litbang.kemendagri.go.id/data-indeks

Furthermore, the Tangerang City was ranked 46 out of 511 cities for its innovation network. Meanwhile, for public service administrative innovation, Tangerang City was ranked 42. A higher rating was obtained for the Information Technology using category, which was ranked 41. Overall, Tangerang City was ranked 50 with a total of 96 innovations produced in 2019-2020.

KIMFesT

In an effort to maximize the potential of the region, the Tangerang city government created a program called KIMFesT which also involves the community, including SMEs, to take advantage of technology. With a technology utilization approach, the Tangerang City Government wants to find information agents to spread the potential of the region. In addition, KIMFest's goal is also to empower local businesses to be ready to face digitalization and increase the capabilities of hundreds of KIM Fest members to promote their products digitally. It started with 4 times webinar training and continued with competitions and closed with a celebration of the winners of the competition. Through this activity, the local government has optimism that the empowerment of KIMFesT members will make a good contribution to improving the regional economy in the future.

KIMFesT is not only presented as a program but also an empowerment. According to Mulyani, Head of the Tangerang City Government Communication and Information Division, KIMFesT is a series of activities and is a competition to implement the knowledge gained from the training that can be useful for others. Mulyani added, the total prize to be awarded was IDR 63 million. KIM members are ambassadors for promoting resources in their environment. The local government proudly claims that this agenda can help and motivate other social communities in the city of Tangerang to be creative and innovative in the pandemic era. In Tangerang City, there are various KIM members who form various activities and are spread across 13 sub-districts.

Picture 1. KIMFesT Activities

Source: diskominfo.tangerangkota.go.id

Tangerang BISA

Another program that supports SMEs carried out by the Tangerang City Government is Tangerang BISA or the Start-up Grant Incentive and Tangerang UKM. This program was developed as business capital assistance for novice entrepreneurs who will start a business or develop a business during the Covid-19 pandemic. This program is integrated with the Tangerang LIVE Application platform that was previously created by the Tangerang City Government. To get grant incentives, applicants must register an account at <https://sabakota.tangerangkota.go.id/>. Then, applicants fill out the requirements that must be completed. Furthermore, officers at Sabakota will verify all incoming applications and make visits to locations, places of sale, and other existing checks. If all the requirements are complete, the mayor will issue a decree to register the list of recipients of the Tangerang BISA grant incentive.

There are currently 388 applicants in Sabakota. However, to get the Tangerang BISA grant incentive for Start-ups and SMEs they have to go through a long stage. Below are the 7 steps to get the Tangerang BISA.

Picture 2. The Procedure to Get Tangerang BISA Incentives

Source: sabakota.tangerangkota.go.id

Based on Douay's forms of urban planning, Tangerang City has been adopting Wiki Urban Planning to promote start-up and SMEs to improve their welfare. It can be understood that Tangerang city

government seek on alternative model by involving start-up, SMEs, and community participate in advancing the city, in this case by promoting their products digitally.

Furthermore, we can see the efforts of the Tangerang City government with a smart city approach and the use of innovation through the five points mentioned by Green (2019). First, Tangerang city government attempt to offers solution by guiding start-up and SMEs in social community to improve their welfare through various infrastructures and incentives; Second, All stakeholders in Tangerang city government have been engage with social community to use digital technology in public service; Third, Tangerang city government has prioritize innovation policy by applying smart governance in public service; Fourth, there is a reciprocal relationship between the Tangerang City Government and the community, namely that the community receives training and incentives for start-ups and SMEs while the government benefits from the active role of the community in disseminating their knowledge to the wider community; Last, Although this program has just been implemented, it has the potential to be developed so that the data obtained are integrated with other departments in the city (eg. integration of business incentives with business licenses, etc.).

Conclusion

To help meet the needs of the community and turn the technological transformation challenges into opportunities, local governments must make a transition to a smart city model in their public services.. All actors must have good preparedness competencies and good governance. Based on a literature review in Douay, the Tangerang City government has adopted the Wiki Urban Planning to encourage small and medium-sized entrepreneurs (SMEs) to achieve their prosperity. Furthermore, the Tangerang City Government is already good at implementing smart cities and has great potential for development. As a result, the smart city model in the Tangerang City Government has been organized and can be a best practice for other cities or provinces in Indonesia to follow, especially to support SMEs in the context of smart cities. As a smart city improvement in Tangerang City, it is recommended to refer to the Technopolies model that satellite cities require hi-tech innovation, connected to telecommunications towards a new era of decentralized smart city development.

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